

Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on international research collaboration: A pilot survey results

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Introduction

COVID-19 has caused catastrophic disruptions at the socio-economic levels. Understanding how this pandemic impacted international collaboration is essential to inform program interventions and foster a more connected and resilient global research community (Bogle, 2020; Lee & Haupt, 2021). Issues such as hiring freezes, stopped lab and fieldwork, delayed research infrastructure, socio-cognitive health impacts, plagued flow of international students, and constrained travel disrupted international research collaborations (Gewin, 2020; Radecki & Schonfeld, 2020; Recio & Colella, 2020).

Since the early 1990s, developed and developing countries have observed a 10- and 20- times rise in internationally co-authored scientific publications (Gewin, 2020). Nearly a quarter of all scientific publications globally are attributed to international collaborations, generating higher citations and more significant societal impacts across the globe (Gewin, 2020; Lee & Haupt, 2021; Miroudot, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic, however, throttled this momentum (Liu et al., 2020; Miroudot, 2020) through a complete disruption in travel, face-to-face interactions, lab work, fieldwork, hiring, and the flow of international students (Bogle, 2020; Brandon-Jones et al., 2014; Gewin, 2020; Radecki & Schonfeld, 2020; Recio & Colella, 2020). This disruption not just plagued discovery and shared scientific progress, particularly in international research, but also choked the national capacity to keep offering a skilled workforce (Bogle, 2020; Brandon-Jones et al., 2014; Gewin, 2020).

Adverse impacts on international research collaborations ranged from cost overruns, human resource limitations, and shutdown of research facilities that diminished research and training opportunities for underrepresented minorities (Bogle, 2020; Radecki & Schonfeld, 2020; Recio & Colella, 2020). Understanding how international collaborations can be made more robust and resilient, particularly to the shocks of a global crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic, is lacking (Bogle, 2020; Gewin, 2020). Changes in how scholars currently perform international research are

necessary to manage similar potential conditions in the future (Liu et al., 2020). An integrated understanding of how this pandemic influenced active global research collaborations is integral in identifying research and infrastructure gaps and informing current and future international research programs. This study represents the pilot part of a project through which time-sensitive qualitative and quantitative data from active international research projects were collected and synthesized to explain significant gaps, interventions, and opportunities for international collaboration. This paper aims to reveal how the pandemic affected international research collaboration, specifically its robustness, resilience, and sustainability.

Methodology

This paper represents the results of a pilot survey conducted at a public research university in the U.S. The online survey included eleven questions on 5-point Likert scales to rate the impact of the pandemic on international research collaboration and its indicators. 31 participants completed the survey. A descriptive statistic was used to describe the basic features of the collected data. The survey questions centered on three components of global research collaboration: team dynamics, project logistics, and research operations.

Results

Under the construct robustness, participants answered six questions, which inquired how pandemic created challenges, conflicts, or limitations impacted global collaboration. The rounded means of responses indicate that participants rated the impact of the challenges, conflicts, and limitations caused by COVID-19 on international research operations and project logistics as more severe than team dynamics. The rounded means also show that the COVID-19 challenges, conflicts, and limitations impacted the research process more than the research outcomes. The rounded means also denote a major impact of constrained travel and facilities shutdown caused by COVID-19 on research projects. Four out of the six

questions under the construct robustness had a rounded mean of 4.0, which may demonstrate robustness having a major impact on global collaboration.

Participants responded to seven questions under the construct resilience that examined to what extent the remedial interventions or changes explored by research teams were effective on the three components, project logistics, research operation, and team dynamics. The rounded means indicate that the changes and interventions explored by research teams affected project logistics more than team dynamics and research operations. However, these interventions and changes were only moderately effective to keep the three research components as planned, showing that any remedial measures taken by the research teams were not highly effective in keeping the research on track. The rounded means also show that such changes and interventions only moderately influenced the overall research quality. Additionally, based on the rounded means under the construct resilience, participants rated 85.7% of the seven indicators of international collaboration integral to its resilience as moderate and only 14.3% of the seven indicators as major.

The next five questions examined if and to what extent the project's sustainability was impacted by the pandemic. The rounded means show that the impact of the pandemic on the project schedule was more severe than the project budget and health/safety of the team. Participants seem to agree that the role of virtual communication technologies was excellent during this adverse period. Participants rated the impact of time zone differences on their projects as negligible. Based on the rounded means under the construct sustainability, the most severe impact of the pandemic was on the project schedules.

The last question asked participants to rate the overall impact of the pandemic on international research collaboration. The rounded mean of responses indicate that participants believed that the overall impact of the pandemic on international research collaboration was moderate.

Conclusions

The findings of this study indicated the overall impact of the pandemic on international research collaboration was considered moderate. The pandemic affected a higher percentage of the indicators of international collaboration integral to its robustness severely than those integral to its resilience or sustainability. Consequently, focusing on the aspects integral to its robustness is the most relevant for remedial actions to decrease the shocks of a global crisis on international research collaboration. In addition, focusing on research operations, project logistics, and research process may be more promising for increasing the robustness of international research collaboration. The most

effective remedial measures are necessary for project logistics to increase international collaboration resilience. Finding ways to follow project timelines may be crucial to making international collaboration more sustainable. The findings inform the design and management of global research collaborations for robustness, resilience, and sustainability to adverse situations such as those created by the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic.

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